

STRUCTURE OF A BY-PRODUCT OBTAINED DURING THE
CLEMMENSEN REDUCTION OF β -(*p*-CYMOYL-2)-
PROPIONIC ACID

BY SUKH DEV

A by-product, m. p. 210-11°, obtained during the Clemmensen reduction of β -(*p*-cymoyl-2)-propionic acid, has been found to be a pinacol-dilactone. The structure has been confirmed by synthesis.

During the synthesis of *apo*-cadalene (Sukh Dev and Guha, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 14) β -(*p*-cymoyl-2)-propionic acid (I) was subjected to Clemmensen reduction (Martin's procedure). Besides the normal reduction product, γ -(*p*-cymyl-2)-butyric acid, a small amount of a high melting substance was found also to be formed. A number of similar instances have been recorded previously. A solid of m. p. 254° can be isolated as a by-product of the Clemmensen reduction of β -benzoylpropionic acid, for which Fieser has proposed a structure of a pinacol-dilactone ("Organic Syntheses", Vol XV, p. 64). Huang-Minlon (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 2487) has also obtained a similar by-product during the Clemmensen reduction (Martin's procedure) of β -(*p*-phenoxybenzoyl)-propionic acid. The production of dimeric substances during the Clemmensen reduction of aromatic ketones is quite common, for example, benzophenone is known to yield dimeric products to the extent of 72-75%; this problem has been investigated by Bradlow and Vander-Werf (*ibid.*, 1947, 69, 1254).

Fieser (*loc. cit.*) and Huang-Minlon (*loc. cit.*) have provisionally assigned a structure of a pinacol-dilactone for their by-products, probably, only on the basis of the combustion analysis. The insolubility of our product in hot 20% aqueous caustic potash led us to decide against a lactone structure. A reinvestigation of the substance has, however, revealed that though the product is not attacked by hot aqueous alkali, the lactone ring is easily cleaved by hot alcoholic potassium hydroxide. Molecular weight determinations and analysis indicate a similar structure (II) for this product also.

In order to confirm the structure, the substance has been prepared by a straight-forward method. Newman (*ibid.*, 1940, 62, 1683) has developed a new synthesis of coronene, which involves the important step of pinacol reduction of 7-methyl-1-tetralone. He has discovered a new and efficient reagent in aluminium-mercury and absolute alcohol for effecting such pinacolic reductions. Thomas and Nathan (*ibid.*, 1948, 70, 333) have also successfully employed his method. By using this procedure a pinacol-dilactone has been synthesised

from β -(*p*-cymoyl-2)-propionic acid, which has been found to be identical with the by-product of the Clemmensen reduction in all respects.

In as much as the pinacols can be the by-products of the normal alcoholic reduction of ketones, the production of these substances may have some bearing on the mechanism of Clemmensen reduction of β -aroyl-propionic acids. The formation of pinacol-dilactones may indicate that the monomeric lactones may be the intermediates. In fact, γ -phenylbutyrolactone is known to give about as good a yield of γ -phenylbutyric acid as does β -benzoylpropionic acid (Martin, *ibid.*, 1936, 58, 1440).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

*Clemmensen Reduction of β -(*p*-Cymoyl-2)-propionic Acid: Isolation of the by-product.*—The by-product was isolated in exactly the same way as described by Sukh Dev and Guha (*this Journal*, 1948, 25, 18). By using a slight excess of glacial acetic acid during the reduction, the yield of the by-product can be somewhat increased. This is probably due to the resulting higher concentration of the keto-acid in the acid phase of the reaction mixture which is favourable to dimeric condensations.

The product of m. p. 210–11° on further recrystallisations from 90% acetic acid was obtained in small, silvery white, feathery needles, m p 214–15°. (Found: C, 77.01; H, 8.0; M. W., 428. $C_{28}H_{34}O_4$ requires C, 77.41; H, 7.83 per cent. M. W., 434).

Action of Alcoholic Potash.—The substance (50 mg.) was added to 5% alcoholic potash (10 c.c.) and the mixture was refluxed for 2 hours, cooled and most of the alcohol was distilled off. The residue was taken up in water (5 c.c.) and the clear solution filtered. The filtrate was concentrated a little and then acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitated substance was filtered off, washed with water and recrystallised from acetic acid (90%), m. p. 214–15° (mixed m.p. with the original substance, 214–15°).

*Pinacolic Reduction of β -(*p*-Cymoyl-2)-propionic Acid.*— β -(*p*-Cymoyl-2)-propionic acid (5.0 g.) was dissolved in a mixture of absolute alcohol

(30 c.c.) and thiophene-free benzene (dry, 20 c.c.). Bright aluminium foil, freshly cut into small bits (2.0 g.) and mercuric chloride (0.1g.) were added in quick succession. The mixture was swirled for a few minutes and then refluxed on a steam-bath for 4 hours. More of absolute alcohol (15 c.c.) was then added and the refluxing continued for another 2 hours, after which practically all the aluminium had disappeared and the reaction mixture had become pasty and grey. The reaction was completed by refluxing for 6 hours more. The mixture was cooled, and added on to ice and hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.). Some ether was added and the whole transferred to a separating funnel and shaken vigorously till all the aluminium salts had completely disappeared. The product was extracted with ether (thrice) and the combined ether extracts were washed with dilute hydrochloric acid (once), and finally with water (once). The ether solution was then washed with 5% sodium carbonate solution (thrice) to remove the acidic components which were not further examined. The solvent layer was washed twice with water and finally dried (sodium sulphate). On removal of the solvent, a solid was left which was twice recrystallised from 90% acetic acid. The pinacol-dilactone was obtained in fine, silvery white needles, crystallising in rosettes, m.p. 214-15°. A mixed m.p. with a sample of the Clemmensen reduction by-product remained undepressed.

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ORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORIES,
DEPARTMENT OF PURE AND APPLIED CHEMISTRY,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE, BANGALORE.

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